

Studies on heterobimetallic complexes of diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on $M^{II}Hg^{II}L$ mixed metal/heterobimetallic complexes, where M^{II} represents Be^{II} , Cd^{II} , Co^{II} metal ions and L the ligand diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) using Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique in aqueous solution at an ionic strength 0.1 M (KNO_3) and temperatures 20 and 40°. Studies reveal the formation of $[Be^{II}Hg^{II}DTPA]^-$, $[Cd^{II}Hg^{II}DTPA]^-$ and $[Co^{II}Hg^{II}DTPA]^-$ species for which equilibrium constants have been evaluated. The values of overall changes in free energy, enthalpy and entropy, accompanying complex formation have also been evaluated.

The aminopolycarboxylic acids including DTPA having a large number of donor sites are of great significance as they have been used as antidote compounds in heavy metal intoxication, and thus can be used to develop a successful therapeutic protocol for heavy metal intoxication¹ and also newer chelating and sequestering agents in biological and industrial processes². Moreover, possibly the formation of mixed-metal complexes with polydentate ligands³ offers a new and interesting field for coordination chemistry in solution.

The present studies throw light on the complexation equilibria of the potential polydentate ligands which are used as sequestering agents for biotoxic metal ions such as Hg^{II} , Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} .

Results and Discussion

pH-titration curves of the systems are presented in Fig. 1.

The 1 : 1 Hg^{II} DTPA complex has very high stability and the reported value of log *K* by different techniques is 27.0. On the other hand, the 1 : 1 metal-DTPA complexes

chosen for the present study have lower log *K* values. The literature values⁴ of log *K* for such 1 : 1 metal-DTPA complexes (in 0.1 M KNO_3 , at 20°) are as follows : cadmium(II) 19.00; cobalt(II) 19.96; mercury(II) 27.00.

Since the stability of H_3Hg^{II} DTPA complex is more than 10^6 to 10^8 times greater than that of the other reported complexes, it can be presumed that in a 1 : 1 $M^{II}H_3Hg^{II}$ -DTPA reaction mixture, Hg^{II} remains fully complexed and the reaction mixture mainly contains the species H_3Hg^{II} -DTPA and M^{II} at low pH (i.e. pH lower than 2.5). This reaction condition is maintained in the reaction mixture by adding requisite amount of perchloric acid. When the pH of this mixture is raised by adding KOH, the dissociable H^+ ions of the carboxylic groups of H_3Hg^{II} DTPA are displaced as per following equilibria,

The completely deprotonated ligand which becomes available in greater quantity with raising pH interacts with the M^{II} forming the heterobimetallic complex $[M^{II}Hg^{II}DTPA]^-$ as per the equilibrium,

H_3Hg^{II} DTPA complex is expected to involve four-coordinate tetrahedral arrangement of coordinate bonds around Hg^{II} , as this is the most preferred coordination number for Hg^{II} . It is reported that octahedral or higher coordination for Hg^{II} is rare and the compounds involving coordination numbers less than four have lower stability⁵. In the species H_3Hg^{II} DTPA, where the Hg^{II} is bound to two nitrogen and two carboxylic groups in a tetrahedral fashion, it has still some vacant coordination sites available for interaction with other metal ions and thus making to the formation of heterobimetallic complex possible of the type $[M^{II}Hg^{II}DTPA]^-$ involving the possible equilibria as :

Fig. 1. pH titration curves for (A) acid, (B) acid + ligand, (C) acid + ligand + Hg^{II} , and acid + ligand + Hg^{II} + M^{II} [i.e. Be^{II} , Cd^{II} , Co^{II} at 20° and $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (KNO_3) with KOH (0.404 M).

The stability constants for above heterobimetallic/mixed-metal complexes have been determined at temperatures 20 and 40° by using the equation,

$$\log k = [\log (\text{TCL}_0 \times \bar{n}) - \log \{\text{TCM}_0 \times (1 - \bar{n})\} + pL]$$

and are as follows : 3.23, 1.65, 1.63 at 20° and 3.25, 1.64, 1.62 at 40° for the Be^{II}, Cd^{II} and Co^{II} complexes respectively (relative error ± 0.1).

The values of overall changes in the free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) accompanying complex formation have also been evaluated by using the method described elsewhere⁶. These values have been evaluated at only one ionic strength and they qualitatively reflect the change in thermodynamic parameters and are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Thermodynamic parameters for $[\text{M}^{\text{n+}}\text{Hg}^{\text{II}}\text{DTPA}]^{\text{n-3}}$ heterobimetallic complexes*

Complex species	ΔG		ΔH	ΔS	
	kJ mol ⁻¹			JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	
	20°	40°	kJ mol ⁻¹	20°	40°
[Be ^{II} Hg ^{II} DTPA] ⁻	-18.12	-19.48	+1.76	+67.85	+67.86
[Cd ^{II} Hg ^{II} DTPA] ⁻	-9.26	-9.83	-0.89	-8.61	-28.60
[Co ^{II} Hg ^{II} DTPA] ⁻	-5.78	-9.71	-51.80	-157.10	-134.50

*Relative error : ±0.2.

Experimental

Solutions of Be^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II} and Hg^{II} metal ions were prepared and standardised by EDTA titrations⁷. A 0.1 M solution of diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) was prepared by dissolving it into two equivalent NaOH prepared in double-distilled water. Solutions of carbonate-free NaOH (E. Merck) and perchloric acid (A.R.) were standardised potentiometrically.

A digital pH-meter (Century Cp 901-S) with a glass electrode (reproducibility 0.01 pH) was used.

The four reaction mixtures were prepared as follows : (A) 10.0 ml KNO₃ (0.5 M) + 10.0 ml HClO₄ (0.1 M) +

water; (B) 10.0 ml KNO₃ (0.5 M) + 10.0 ml HClO₄ (0.1 M) + 5.0 ml DTPA (0.1 M) + water; (C) 10.0 ml KNO₃ (0.5 M) + 10.0 ml HClO₄ (0.1 M) + 5.0 ml DTPA (0.1 M) + 5.0 ml Hg^{II} ion solution (0.1 M) + water; (D) 10.0 ml KNO₃ (0.5 M) + 10.0 ml HClO₄ (0.1 M) + 5.0 ml DTPA (0.1 M) + 5.0 ml Hg^{II} ion solution (0.1 M) + 5.0 ml M^{II} ion solution (0.1 M) + water. The solutions were prepared such that the concentrations of the common ingredients were identical in all the cases. The total volume in each case was kept at 50.0 ml and the ionic strength 0.1 M (KNO₃) and free acid concentration 0.02 M (HClO₄) were also kept the same in each case. The ratio of M^{II} : Hg^{II} : DTPA was kept 1 : 1 : 1. The solutions were then individually titrated against standard alkali solution. The pH-meter readings with progressive addition of alkali to the titration mixture were noted.

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